

It has been observed from the values of overall formation constants that the increase in percentage of methanol and DMSO makes the values of overall formation constant to increase. This may be attributed to the less solvation of the cadmium ion by methanol or DMSO than by water, if solvation is considered to be the only factor affecting the overall formation constant^{8,9}. Otherwise there are many other factors which can affect formation constant viz. density, dielectric constant⁹, viscosity¹⁰, may also be effective in this regard. Moreover ion-pair formation¹¹ plays its role in this case. The increase in the values of overall formation constants in aqueous-nonaqueous media is in complete agreement with similar studies by other workers^{1,2,13}.

In case of isopropanol-water, *n*-propanol-water and formamide water mixed media of various compositions, the values of overall-formation constants are less than those are in pure water.

The relative distribution of the simple Cd(II) and complexed with N-[(β -aminoethyl)]-ethanolamine as function of ligand concentration advocates that the amount of Cd(II) decreases as ligand concentration increases⁷.

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Synthesis of *p*-Alkyl-(2-benzimidazolyl)-methyl-aminobenzoates and Corresponding Hydrazides as Possible Antimalarial Agents

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A series of esters of *p*-(2-Benzimidazolyl)methyl-aminobenzoic acid (I, Y=OR) has been synthesised. One such ester (Y=OEt) on hydrazinolysis furnished the corresponding hydrazide (I, Y=NH.NH₂) which when condensed with different aromatic aldehydes yielded Schiff's bases (I, Y=NH.N=CHR). Reduction of Schiff's base with sodium-borohydride proceeded smoothly to give I (Y=NH.NHCH₂R). Representative compounds when screened, were found inactive as antimalarial.

A number of benzimidazoles have been synthesised and tested as antimalarial agents^{1,2}. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to synthesise such substituted benzimidazole derivatives containing *p*-aminobenzoic acid. The different esters and hydrazides of *p*-(2-benzimidazolyl)methylaminobenzoic acid have been prepared³. The hydrazide was then condensed with aldehydes⁴ and the Schiff's bases thus obtained were reduced to the corresponding secondary amines⁵.

Bio-Assay :

Eleven compounds were screened for antimalarial activity against *P. berghei*-Albino Mice (Swiss) model. None of them was found to be active as antimalarial.

Specification of Host-(Wt = 18-20 gm), sex-male Inoculum : 1 × 10 infected Red cells/animal in 0.25 ml.

Experimental

Melting points were determined in open capillaries and are not corrected. Infrared were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 137G spectrophotometer in KBr.

Ethyl-p-(2-benzimidazolyl)methylaminobenzoates ;
(I, Y = OC₂H₅)

Equimolar quantities of 2-chloromethyl-benzimidazole and ethyl-*p*-aminobenzoate were refluxed in ethanol in presence of small amount of sodium iodide for 12 hr. The solid separated on cooling

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF I

Compound No.	Y	Molecular formula	M. Pt. °C	Yield %
1.	-OCH ₃	C ₁₆ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	233	50
2.	-OEt	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	255	50
3.	-OPr	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂	222	60
4.	-OBu	C ₁₉ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	216	50
5.	-NHNH ₂	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ N ₂ O ₂	240	70
6.	NHN=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .OH-(o)	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂	244	50
7.	NHN=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (m)	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₃	248	40
8.	NHN=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .Br(p)	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₂ OBr	230	45
9.	NH.N=CH.C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ N ₂ O	216	60
10.	NH.N=CH.C ₆ H ₅ .OCH ₃ (m)-OH(p)	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	252	60
11.	NH.N=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (p)	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	225	50
12.	NH.N=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .Cl(p)	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ Cl	238	55
13.	NH.N=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (o)	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂	228	50
14.	NH.N=CH.C ₄ H ₉ O(o)	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂	232	60
15.	NH.N=CH.C ₆ H ₄ .OH(p)	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₂ O ₂	255	80
16.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .OH(o)	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	240	80
17.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (m)	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	242	80
18.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .Br(p)	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ OBr	238	80
19.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₅	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O	242	80
20.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₅ .OCH ₃ (m)OH(p)	C ₂₂ H ₂₃ N ₂ O ₂	235	80
21.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (p)	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	232	80
22.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .Cl(p)	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ OCl	233	80
23.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .NO ₂ (o)	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	234	80
24.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₄ H ₉ O(o)	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	242	80
25.	NH.NH.CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄ .OH(p)	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₂ O ₂	248	80

- a. The elemental analyses were within satisfactory limits.
 b. IR : 1. 2.99(NH), 5.8(C=O), 6.2(C=N), 6.8-7 (alkyl)
 5. 3.0(NH), 5.95(C=O), 6.25(C=N)
 13. 3.10(NH), 6.0(C=O), 6.2(C=N), 6.60 and 7.60(NO₂).
 c. All the compounds were recrystallised from ethanol.

was filtered and washed with ethanol and recrystallised. Me, Pr, Bu esters were also prepared in the same way.

p-(2-Benzimidazolyl)methylaminobenzoic acid hydrazide (I, Y = NH.NH₂)

Ethyl-*p*-(2-benzimidazolyl)methylaminobenzoate (0.01 mole) and hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mole) were refluxed in absolute ethanol for 10 hr. Excess of solvent was removed and the hydrazide, thus separated, was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Hydrazones (I, Y = NH.N = CHAr)

Equimolar quantities of hydrazide and aldehyde were refluxed in ethanol, containing 3 drops of AcOH, for 6 hr. The solid separated was filtered and recrystallised.

Reduction of hydrazones : formation of I (Y = NH.NH.CH₂Ar)

A 10% methanolic solution of sodium borohydride was added with stirring into a 10% methanolic solution of Schiff's base during 30 min. The mixture was heated for 15 min under reflux. Excess of

methanol was removed and the secondary amine was isolated by the addition of water. It was filtered and recrystallised.

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